

Root-zone placement of carbofuran for insect control in rice

S. Y. Choi, College of Agriculture, Seoul National University, Suweon, Korea, and J. K. Ryu, H. R. Lee, and Y. H. Song, Institute of Agricultural Sciences, Office of Rural Development, Suweon, Korea

A root-zone liquid-insecticide injector designed at IRRI was tested in 1976 experiments at Suweon and at Honam. Its effectiveness was compared with that of root-zone applications of encapsulated carbofuran and with broadcast applications. At Suweon, capsules applied to the root zone most effectively controlled the striped stem borer *Chilo suppressalis* and the small brown planthopper *Laodelphax striatellus*. One application with the injector at transplanting was equal to two broadcast applications.

Root-zone and paddy-water applications of insecticide to control insects of rice. Variety Palk-weng.^a Honam Crops Experiment Station, Korea, 1976.

Treatment ^b	Rate (kg a.i./ha) of application	Deadhearts at 55 DT	Insects (no./40 hills)		Yield (t/ha)
			Small brown planthoppers at 30 DT	Green leafhoppers ^c at 40 DT	
Carbofuran Capsules	1.0 x 1	0.6 a	2 a	16 ab	5.350 a
	2.0 x 1	0.3 a	1 a	2 a	5.673 a
Liquid injector	1.0 x 1	8.6 bc	72 ab	50 abc	4.130 bc
	2.0 x 1	4.6 ab	14 ab	15 ab	4.339 b
Broadcast	0.9 x 2	16.7 cd	65 ab	64 abc	4.050 bcd
	0.9 x 4	8.1 ab	52 ab	33 abc	4.473 b
Diazinon Broadcast	0.9 x 2	16.9 d	101 ab	74 bc	3.555 cd
	0.9 x 4	5.0 ab	156 b	60 abc	3.757 bcd
Control		19.3 d	114 ab	80 c	3.356 d

^aJaponica-type variety susceptible to common rice insect pests in Korea. Within a column, means that are followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. DT days after transplanting. ^bFirst application, 2 days after transplanting. ^c*Nephotettix cincticeps*.

At Honam, capsules also were the most effective. One application of

carbofuran by injector was equal to four broadcast applications (see table).

Number and duration of larval instars of striped rice borer *Chilo suppressalis* in the laboratory

J. Soejitno, Entomology Department, Central Research Institute for Agriculture, Bogor, Indonesia

The larval instars of *C. suppressalis* were studied in the laboratory at CRIA, Bogor. Larvae were reared on 5- to 7-day-old

seedlings of IR5. Twenty-five larvae were sampled at 3-day intervals during larval development and the width of their head capsules was measured under the microscope. Daily observations were also made of individually reared larvae to determine the time of molting and duration of each instar.

Data on the larval head width, plotted as frequency distributions, showed six

distinct peaks (see figure), which indicated six larval instars (L1-L6). The major part of the larval population molted six times (65%) and only a minor part molted five (19%) or seven times (16%). The larval instars of *C. suppressalis* can be estimated by measuring head capsule width.

The mean value of the head width of instars L1, L2, L3, L4, L5, and L6 was 0.28 mm, 0.39 mm, 0.58 mm, 0.84 mm, 1.11 mm, and 1.46 mm, respectively. The mean duration of the larval instars varied from 5 to 6 days and the average larval stadium was 31 days.

Frequency (no. of larvae)

Frequency distribution of larval head width of *Chilo suppressalis* reared on IR5 rice seedlings.

Seedling root-coat treatment with carbofuran

J. N. Seiber, visiting scientist; E. A. Heinrichs, entomologist; and S. A. Valencia, research aide, Entomology Department, International Rice Research Institute

Soaking rice seedlings in a solution of carbofuran and water gives some early protection against such pests as whorl maggot and green leafhopper. The addition of perlite, a porous volcanic mineral soil conditioner, to the soaking solution extends the period of protection. Suspended perlite coats the seedling roots and acts as a reservoir for further